

Symmetric Spaces, Fermions, and Planchifolds

Ryan J. Buchanan

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Abstract

Planchifolds are re-derived using a nervous

The following:

$$\int_K f(\phi) \tag{0.1}$$

$$= \int_{\bigcup_i K_i} (f^+(\phi) \oplus f^-(\phi)) \tag{0.2}$$

where

$$\phi = \langle \sum_i \phi_i \rangle \tag{0.3}$$

is the “pure field,” and shall be denoted here and forever after by ϕ_{Pur} , and abbreviated as PF. It corresponds to a torsionless Weitzenböck connection over a pure scalar field ϕ , and reads as a massless field of energy.

We make the identification:

$$\phi_0 = z \cap \bar{z} = \nu_{\mathbf{E}} \tag{0.4}$$

so that the energetic center of X lies at the origin of the pure field.

We have:

$$\pi_y(\phi_{Pur}) := \mathbb{Z} \quad \forall y \leq \mathcal{N} \tag{0.5}$$

1 Fermionization

The map

$$K_i \longrightarrow K_j$$

given by

$$y \mapsto y^{p/2}$$

lifts the trace elements of all plurisubharmonic functions over our locally ringed space $(X, \mathcal{O}_X)$ to bonafide subharmonics.

The ring of fractions, ξK , maps into K_j for all $j > i$, and the map $K_i \longrightarrow K_j$, called the “fermionization,” is injective. For every $\tilde{i} \subseteq i$, define an injection $\tilde{i} \hookrightarrow \tilde{j}$ (denoted by ι) given by

$$\tilde{j} = \xi^{2/p} j$$

2 Nerves

Where do nerves come into play?

$$\mathcal{N}_K^n := \xi^{n-1}(K) = \xi^{-n}(K) \quad (2.1)$$

The most special nerve is the Koszul nerve:

$$\mathcal{N}(K) = \mathcal{N}_K^1 \quad (2.2)$$

which is an $(\infty, 1)$ -category (all cells are isomorphisms). The topological space created by mapping morphisms to paths is called a “planchifold.” (Emmerson)

Planchifolds play a role in non-critical string theory

3 Questions

Define a functor

$$\varrho : \mathcal{N}(K) \longrightarrow \mathit{Fuk}_K \quad (3.1)$$

What are the properties of this functor, where Fuk_K is the category whose objects are A -branes, and whose morphisms are smooth deformations?